

THE TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND THE CORRELATION WITH THE TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The correlation of the fracture toughness and the damage tolerance behaviour is a major research topic up to now. A problem is that when comparing materials with different toughnesses also other material properties are different. In this approach the fracture toughness was varied by varying the test temperature. The data was compared with the impact behaviour of thick and thin structures under the same test temperatures. The thin structures showed a good correlation with the Mode II fracture toughness, whereas the thick structures showed a better correlation with the Mode I toughness. The compressive strength showed no clear correlation with the toughness.

Keywords: Fracture toughness, impact, residual strength, temperature

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last years the correlation of the fracture toughness and the damage tolerance behaviour has been a major research topic. Today the testing of the Mode I and Mode II fracture toughness is standard in material characterization. For a wide range of materials these toughnesses have been tested [1,2,3]. Also impact testing is performed with a lot of materials. Especially the compression after impact test CAI [4] is often used. But in spite of these efforts the results concerning the correlation are not satisfactory.

There have been some investigations concerning the correlation of fracture toughness and impact performance. Lee [5] reported of a nearly linear correlation of Mode I fracture toughness and the compressive strength after impact.

Garwins [6] results show no clear correlation. Masters [7] found that there is no correlation of Mode I fracture toughness and the compressive strength after impact, but he found a linear correlation between the Mode II fracture toughness and the residual strength.

The problem is that for the variation of fracture toughness different materials are taken. But when comparing materials with different fracture toughnesses also other material properties are quite different. A composite consists of fibre and matrix, and both fibre and matrix have an influence as well on the fracture toughness as on other material properties [8,9]. So when the impact response of materials is different, it may be the result of different toughnesses, but they may be also a result of differences in other material properties.

In the present approach an other way was chosen. Only one material was used and the variation of the fracture toughness was achieved by varying the test temperature. Of course also here material properties change with the temperature, but there is no influence through a different fibre typ. The changes in other material properties are mostly relatively small, and the temperature dependence of the material properties is known. Table 1 shows the most important material data at different test temperatures. The used material was the Narmco 5208 with the Celion G30/500 fibre.

Properties	Unit	-54 °C	RT	132 °C	177 °C
0° Tensile Strength	MPa	1344	1586	1482	1413
0° Tensile Modulus	MPa	145000	143000	141000	136000
0° Tensile Strain	%	0,9	1,0	1,0	0,9
90° Tensile Strength	MPa	43	52	41	30
90° Tensile Modulus	MPa	10600	8600	7600	6600
90° Tensile Strain	%	0,4	0,5	0,4	0,3
0° Compression Strength	MPa	1544	1503	1186	1138
0° Compression Modulus	MPa	140000	136000	127000	122000
0° Compression Strain	%	1,1	1,1	0,9	0,9
ILS	MPa	139	117	83	67

Table 1: Material properties at different temperatures [10]

2. THE TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

For the Mode I fracture toughness testing standard DCB specimens were taken [11] and for Mode II testing ELS and ENF specimens [12,13]. The testing was done without unloading and loading loops. The data reduction scheme is reported elsewhere [14,15]. Figure 1 shows the Mode I fracture toughness over the temperature.

As other investigators found [16,17], the Mode I fracture toughness increases with increasing temperature. At 0°C there seems to be a minimum of fracture toughness, but this is not confirmed by the other investigators. Figure 2 shows the Mode II fracture toughness.

There is a clear decreasing tendency with the temperature. There is a good correlation to the interlaminar shear strength, as seen in table 1. Figure 3 shows the trend lines of interlaminar shear strength and Mode II fracture toughness.

Figure 1: Mode I fracture toughness over the temperature

Figure 2: Mode II fracture toughness over the temperature

this confirms the theoretical correlation of toughness and strength [18]

$$(1) \quad G_c = \delta \sigma_c$$

δ is a critical crack opening displacement and σ_c is the strength.

Figure 3: Comparison of ILS and G_{IIc}

3. IMPACT RESPONSE

3.1 Flexible Structures

For these tests plates similar to the Boeing Specification BSS 7260 or DIN 65561 were taken. They were only half as thick. They were impacted with a drop weight impactor at 5 energy levels: 2, 4/5/7, 3/9, 6 and 12 J. The impact velocity was 4 m/s. Figures 4 to 6 show the absorbed energy, the delaminated area and the maximum deflection over the temperature.

Figure 4: Absorbed energy of thin plates over the temperature

The absorbed energy is slightly decreasing, whereas the delaminated area and the maximum deflection are constant. So there is a better correlation to the Mode II fracture toughness. The failure is dominated by shear failure. There is also a good correlation between the maximum deflection and the delaminated area. This means that the impact process is quasi static. The maximum deflection and also the maximum contact force can be calculated with the use of simple one or two mass oscillator models like

Figure 5: Delaminated area over the temperature

Figure 6: Maximum deflection over the temperature

that of Caprino [19] or others [20]. A stress analysis in the state of maximum deflection should give the damage area.

These mass oscillator models can only be used for flexible structures. But the stiffness of a structure relative to the impact force, that is the spring stiffness of the one mass oscillator model, is an important property when comparing the impact behaviour of different structures.

3.2 Stiff Structures

Here Charpy Impact specimens were used according DIN 53453. The impact energy was 3,92 J. Figure 7 shows the absorbed energy over the temperature.

Figure 7: Absorbed energy of Charpy specimens over the temperature

Here the absorbed energy is increasing with the temperature. So there is a better correlation to the Mode I fracture toughness for stiff structures. The damage structure in the stiff specimens is different from that in the flexible specimens. In the stiff specimens the damage is a result of stress waves that spread out from the impact point. The largest delaminations are in the middle of the specimen. In the flexible specimens the damage is a result of the deflection. Here the largest delaminations are at the back side of the specimen as figure 8 shows.

Flexible structures

Stiff structures

Figure 8: Damage structures

4. RESIDUAL COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH

The plates were also tested on compression. To avoid buckling the specimen length was reduced to 100mm. The compression tests were performed under the same temperatures as the impact tests. Figure 9 shows the residual strength with reference to the undamaged structure at room temperature.

There is a slight decrease in strength. So there may be a better correlation to the Mode II fracture toughness. But this can also be the result of the decreasing compressive strength of the unidirectional composite as table 1 shows.

Figure 9: Residual strength

Altogether the temperature has only a small influence on the residual compressive strength of impact damaged structures. This is confirmed by the tests of Levin [21].

REFERENCES

- 1 Sela, N., Ishai, O., *Interlaminar Fracture Toughness and Toughening of Laminated Composite Materials: a Review*, Composites, Vol. 20, 1989, pp. 423-435
- 2 Williams, J.G., O'Brien, T.K., Chapman, A.J., *Comparison of Toughened Composite Laminates Using NASA Standard Damage Tolerance Tests*, NASA CP 2321, 1984
- 3 Hoika, B., *Zusammenstellung und Beurteilung von Kriterien für das Wachstum von Delaminationen in Kohlenfaserverstärkten Kunststoffen*, Diplomarbeit, IFB University of Stuttgart, 1989
- 4 Boeing Specification Standard BSS 7260, *Advanced Composite Compression Testing*, 1982
- 5 Lee, S.M., *Compression-After-Impact of Composites with Toughened Matrices*, SAMPE Journal, March/April, 1986, pp. 64-68
- 6 Garwin, I., *Tough Thermosetting Resins with Superior Damage Tolerance Hercules 8551 Series*, 31st International SAMPE Symposium, April 7-10, 1986, pp. 1204-1213
- 7 Masters, J.E., *Correlation of Impact and Interleaf Delamination resistance in Interleafed Laminates*, Proc. 6th Int. Conf. on Comp. Mat./2nd European Conf. on Comp. Mat., edited by F.L. Matthews, N.C.R. Buskell, J.M. Hodgkinson and J. Morton, Elsevier Applied Science Publishers, 1987, pp. 3.96-3.107

- 8 Hunston, D.L., *Composite Interlaminar Fracture: Effect of Matrix Fracture Energy*, Composites Technology Review, Vol. 6, 1984, pp. 176-180
- 9 Fischer, Chr., *Die Interlaminare Reißfähigkeit und ihre Bedeutung für Schlaggeschädigte Kohlenstoffaserverbundstrukturen*, PhD University of Stuttgart, 1993, pp. 49-61
- 10 5208 Prepreg System, Product Information of BASF Structural Materials Inc. 1440 N Kraemer Boulevard Anaheim, California 92806, 1987
- 11 Whitney, J.M., Browning, C.E., Hoogsteden, W., *A Double Cantilever Beam Test for Characterizing Mode I Delamination of Composite Materials*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 16, 1982, pp. 297-313
- 12 Hashemi, S., Kinloch, A.J., Williams, J.G., *Mechanics and Mechanisms of Delamination in a Poly(ether sulphone)-Fibre Composite*, Composite Science & Technology, Vol. 37, 1990, pp. 429-462
- 13 Russel, A.J., Street, K.N., *Moisture and Temperature Effects on the Mixed Mode Delamination Fracture of Unidirectional Graphite/Epoxy*, ASTM STP 876, 1985, pp. 349-370
- 14 Fischer, Chr., Arendts, F.J., *Electrical Crack Length Measurement and the Temperature Dependence of the Mode I Fracture Toughness of Carbonfibre Reinforced Plastics*, Composite Science & Technology, Vol. 43, 1993
- 15 Fischer, Chr., Arendts, F.J., *Eine Methode zur Bestimmung der Reißfähigkeit von faserverstärkten Kunststoffen*, DGLR Jahrbuch, 1990, p. 493
- 16 Hunston, D.L., Bascom, W.D., *Effects of Lay-Up, Temperature and Loading Rate in Double Cantilever Beam Tests of Interlaminar Crack Growth*, Composites Technology Review, Vol. 5, 1983, pp. 118-119
- 17 Hine, P.J., Brew, B., Duckett, R.A., Ward, I.M., *Failure Mechanisms in Continuous Carbon-Fibre Reinforced Composites*, Composite Science & Technology, Vol. 35, 1989, pp. 31-51
- 18 Heckel, K., *Einführung in die Technische Anwendung der Bruchmechanik*, Hanser, München Wien, 1983, p. 196
- 19 Caprino, G., Visconti, I.C., Di Ilio, A., *Elastic Behaviour of Composite Structures, under Low Velocity Impact*, Composites, Vol. 15, 1984, pp. 231-234
- 20 Sjöblom, P.O., Hartness, J.T., *On Low Velocity Impact Testing of Composite Materials*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, 1988, pp. 30-52
- 21 Levin, K., *Effect of Low Velocity Impact on Compressive Strength of Quasi-Isotropic Laminate*, Proceedings of the American Society for Composites, 1. Techn. Conf., Technomic Publishing Co. Inc., Lancaster Basel, 1986, pp. 313-325